

IMPACT RESPONSE OF CARBON CLOTH REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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Summary

A study was undertaken in order to examine the impact behaviour of composite materials under low speed conditions. The examined material was a carbon cloth/vinylester resin composite. Impact tests were carried out utilizing a drop-weight instrumented impact machine CEAST AFS/MK3. From a comparison between the analysis of the damages produced in the impacted samples and the relative force-time curves, it was possible to identify some critical points correlatable with peculiar damage levels. It was found that the first significant load drop, generally construed as first fiber breakage point, is not ascribable to first fiber failure; the latter actually occurs at lower energy levels and is characterized by a slope decrease in the force displacement impact curve. On the other hand, penetration was clearly signalled by load drops in the impact curves. Finally, impact speed is shown to influence the materials impact behaviour.

Introduction

The necessity of composite materials characterization in terms of impact behaviour is particularly evidenced for aircraft applications. In this case, the attractiveness of composite materials might be greatly reduced by the reduction of residual strength after impact.

Much work has been and is being done in order to understand and interpret composite material impact response under low speed conditions.

In the present work the behaviour of carbon cloth/vinylester resin composite laminates under low speed impact is examined. The aim of the study was to verify the possibility of material damage identification through drop-weight tests, carried out on an instrumented impact machine, and to analyze the influence of impact speed on the material properties.

The obtained results, discussed in the following, show that first fiber failure does not necessarily produce a load drop in the force-time ($F - t$) impact curve; first fiber breakage identification may be obtained in a more reliable way by referring to the slope variations of the force-displacement ($F - x$) impact curve. Penetration of the impactor into the tested material is clearly indicated by a consistent load drop in the

F - t curve. As concerns speed effects on the material properties, the latter seem to increase with increasing load rate.

Material and experimental procedures

Carbon cloth/vinylester laminates, 400 x 400 mm² in size, were prepared by hand lay-up of HTS graphite fiber fabric with 70% of the fibers in the warp direction and 30% in the weft direction. Nine layers were stacked for each panel with coincident warp-weft directions to obtain a nominal thickness of 3.5 mm. After press curing, the laminates were cut to obtain square samples, 80 x 80 mm² in size, destined to impact tests.

Impact tests were carried out utilizing a drop weight instrumented impact machine (Advanced Fractoscope System AFS/MK3 produced by CEAST SpA, Turin, Italy) (Fig.1). The samples were clamped by a pneumatic system between two steel plates with a 40 mm diameter hole. The mass of the impactor was 1.5 kg and its hemispherical nose had a 20 mm diameter. Impact energy was varied by changing the height of the fallig impactor between 30 and 2300 mm. This height range yields an impact speed range of 0.8 - 6.7 m/s. The actual impact speed was measured through an infrared photo-cell device available in the machine and automatically recorded by the data acquisition system.

The current value of the contact force, detected by semiconductor strain gauges placed in the impactor tip, is converted into digital form and recorded in a 2048 bytes buffer memory. The digital data of the test are then fed, through an RS 232-C serial interface, to an Apple IIe computer that displays the force-time (F-t) plot on the screen. The curve can be also recorded on floppy disc for later analysis and/or printed on paper.

Fig.1 - Impact machine and data acquisition and processing system

The software implemented on the computer allows to obtain, through adequate algorithms (1) (2), starting from the F-t curve, other impact curves: absorbed energy-time (U-t), displacement-time (x-t), speed-time (v-t) and force-displacement (F-x).

After the impact tests all samples were carefully examined in order to visually detect the presence and size of the induced damage. Some of the impacted samples were burnt in order to verify the presence of the fiber failures as a consequence of the impact.

Results and discussion

The main goals of the present research work were the following: (a) correlation between impact response given by the force-time curve and damage mechanisms produced in the impacted samples; (b) evaluation of the rate sensitivity of the material mechanical properties.

Damage evaluation

Figs.2-4 show three CFRP samples impacted at different energy levels. It must be noted that because of the opaque nature of CFRP composites, it is not possible to visually evaluate the induced damage unless the latter reaches the sample surfaces. The size of the observable surface damage zone was measured and the presence of broken fibers in the external layers was detected. Delamination extension could not be measured.

For samples impacted at low energy levels ($U_0 \leq 3.6$ J) visual examination reveals a rhomboidal convexity, whose major axis coincides with warp direction, on the back side of the sample; a slight concavity is observable on the front side. No evident fiber failure is noticed. The residual deformation suggests the presence of extended delamination and its geometry is accounted for by the different fiber percentage in the weft and warp directions.

For samples impacted at $U_0 = 5.7$ J fiber breakages develop on the front surface in the warp and weft directions. The surface displays the same general characteristics as the lower energy impacted samples but in a more emphasized way; occasional fiber breakage is observed (fig.2).

For samples impacted at higher energy ($U_0 = 10.3$ J) residual deformation and fiber breakage are still more evident, as is shown in fig.3. Moreover on the front surface the formation of four "petals" is observed.

For samples impacted at energies $10.3 \text{ J} < U_0 \leq 19.5$ J, a penetration process takes place with completion of the petals formation phenomenon and

Fig.2 - CFRP laminate impacted at $U_0 = 5.7$ J. Back face

Fig.3 - CFRP laminate impacted at $U_0 = 10.3$ J. Back face

Fig. 4 - CFRP laminate impacted at $U_0 = 14.8$ J. Front face

up to 3.7 m/s when it reaches the value of 40 mm, equal to the hole diameter in the clamping plates. For higher speeds the presence of the clamps prevents a further damage increase.

The minor axis length increases rapidly up to $v_0 \sim 3.7$ m/s when it reaches the value of ~ 22 mm which is only slightly higher than the impactor nose diameter; for higher speeds the minor axis length stays practically constant and seems therefore mainly governed by impactor tip dimension.

Even though at macroscopic visual examination the samples impacted at energy $U_0 \leq 3.6$ J did not evidence fiber breakage, microscopic examination after burning of the resin showed fiber failures also for the lowest energy

Fig.5 - Dimensions d of the visible damage zone versus impact speed v_0 . Δ damage minor axis; \blacktriangle damage major axis

notable reduction of sample local rigidity at impact location (fig.4). Beyond 19.5 J, sample perforation is observed, i.e. the impactor remains fitted in the sample with no rebound after impact.

In conclusion, three energy ranges can be identified:

- (a) first visible fiber breakage ($U_0 = 3.6 - 5.7$ J)
- (b) extended fiber breakage with "petals" formation ($U_0 = 5.7 - 10.3$ J)
- (c) sample penetration ($U_0 = 10.3 - 19.5$ J)

In fig.5 the length of the two axis of the rhomboidal zone, measured on the impacted samples lower surface, is plotted against initial impact speed v_0 . It may be noticed that the major axis length increases rapidly

level ($U_0 = 0.6$ J). Slight fiber breakages were observed in the lowest two carbon layers, subjected to tensile loading during the impact test.

Accordingly the actual damage propagation is demonstrated to proceed from the tension to the compression loaded surface.

This result forms a contrast with what was noticed through visual examination: in the latter case the first fiber failure was observed on the upper sample surface (for $U_0 > 3.6$ J). Macroscopic visual examination therefore seems inadequate for the correct characterization of the reinforcement failure process.

Impact curves

In the case of low-speed impact of a large rigid mass impacting a linearly elastic plate having a small mass (3) (4), a simple analytical model can be utilized for the description of the phenomenon: the plate may be considered as a spring with constant K , where K represents the static force required to produce a unit transverse deflection of the plate (3). In this case the contact force as a function of time is given by (5):

$$F = F_{\max} \sin \pi t / t_c \quad (1)$$

where: $F_{\max} = v_0 \sqrt{m K} \quad (2)$

and $t_c = \pi \sqrt{m/K} \quad (3)$

with v_0 being the speed of the impactor having mass m immediately before the impact. From Eq.(1) it appears that the theoretical $F-t$ curve in the linear elastic field is sinusoidally shaped. Moreover, the maximum load, F_{\max} , during contact is predicted to be a linear function of the impact speed, v_0 , whereas the contact time, t_c , is independent of speed.

The behaviour of impacted laminates in the elastic field was demonstrated to follow the above equations (6). In the case of elasto-plastic behaviour or hysteresis phenomena, the experimental $F-t$ plot diverges from the theoretical prediction as the value of K is not constant during the loading cycle.

From the experimental $F-t$ curve, the other impact curves $U-t$, $x-t$, $v-t$, and $F-x$ are obtained through software analysis. The most useful impact curve for the impact characterization of CFRP proved to be the $F-x$ curve. From this curve it is possible to derive the main impact parameters: maximum force, F_{\max} , and absorbed energy, U . In the following, therefore, only the $F-t$ and the $F-x$ experimental curves will be shown and discussed.

In fig.6 the $F-t$ and $F-x$ curves for an impact speed $v_0 = 6.5$ m/s are shown. The curves evidence three critical points: the first (point A) indicates a significant variation of sample rigidity suggesting the occurrence of failure mechanisms in the material. Beyond point A, the load increases smoothly up to point B, whereupon the load curve shows clearly visible load drops up to point C. Here a dramatic load drop is evidenced, witnessing conspicuous failure processes in the material.

The same qualitative behaviour is observed for all tested samples. The three critical points are detected respectively at ~ 1000 N, ~ 2900 N, and ~ 4500 N. Through the available software it is possible to calculate the energy absorbed by the material for each critical point. The three energy levels associated with each critical point are: ~ 0.3 J, ~ 3.7 J, and ~ 14.5 J.

Point A corresponds to an energy level (0.3 J) at which visual examination was not able to evidence reinforcement failures. Anyway, the slope decrease of the $F-x$ curve at point A suggests the occurrence of a first fiber failure and this hypothesis is also supported by microscopic examination results.

Point B is observed at an energy level comprised in the 3.6 - 5.7 J range where the first visible fiber breakages are observed on the front surface of the sample. The load drops observed in the $F-x$ curve beyond point B

Fig.6 - Contact force F vs. (a) time t and (b) displacement x for impact speed $v_0=6.5$ m/s

Fig.7 - Expanded form of the $F - x$ curve in fig.6 b

cannot therefore be utilized for first fiber failure identification as they may be associated only with extensive material damage.

Point C is evidenced at an energy of ~ 14.5 J which is in the range of penetration development. This point seems to indicate the start of the penetration process associated with the completion of the petals formation: the compliance of the material increases notably and abruptly and its capacity to withstand the impactor thrust lowers considerably.

In order to verify the presence of load drops at the low energy levels at which fiber breakage was detected through microscopic analysis the first part of the $F-x$ curve may be examined after expansion of the axis (fig.7). The expanded section of the curve is provided by the available software.

In fig.7 a load drop at point A is actually observed. Small contact force inversions, however, are visible also for lower force levels. Moreover, the expanded curve, though disturbed by oscillatory phenomena, clearly displays a slope decrease beyond point A.

It is reasonable to question whether the first contact force inversions issue from oscillatory phenomena of the structure under impact

Fig.8 - Contact force F vs. time t for impact speed $v_0=0.89$ m/s. Continuous line: experimental curve. Dotted line: theoretical curve.

Fig.9 - Expanded form of the F - x curve for impact speed $v_0=0.89$ m/s.

should be based on the variations of structure rigidity rather than on load drops or inversions.

Effects of impact speed

In order to verify the influence of load rate on the material impact behaviour, two characteristic events of such behaviour were analyzed: first

or are actually representative of reinforcement failure. Low energy level tests were carried out to clear the point. Fig.8 shows the F - t curve for an impact energy $U_0 = 0.6$ J ($v_0 = 0.89$ m/s). The dotted line represents the theoretical impact curve as predicted by equation (1). The theoretical plot practically coincides with the experimental curve in the first part and diverges from it in the second part starting from a force level of ~ 800 N. This deviation suggests the occurrence of damage phenomena at that force level.

Fig.9 shows the expanded F - x curve of the same test as fig.8; only the first part of the curve is diagrammed. The curve slope stays practically constant up to ~ 800 N and then decreases notably; this observation confirms the hypothesis of failure occurrence at such force level. It is worth remarking that no load is observed: this should indicate that the small contact force inversions evidenced in fig.7 are due to oscillations of the test structure rather than to material damage occurrence.

The above results seem to indicate that a reliable method for first fiber failure identification in the case of CFRP impact testing

fiber breakage and penetration onset. The energy and force level typical of each event may be used for event identification.

In figs.10 and 11 first fiber failure force and energy (F_i and U_i) as well as penetration force and energy (F_p and U_p) are reported versus impact speed. The straight lines in the figures are drawn according to the method of least squares.

Despite data scatter, quite high in some cases, all best fit straight lines evidence an increase of properties with speed. The influence of test speed, though, seem, much more marked for first fiber failure than for penetration onset. In the latter case and in the speed range 4-7 m/s

Fig. 10 - First fiber failure force F_i and energy U_i versus impact speed v_o . Δ Force; \blacktriangle Energy

Fig.11 - Penetration force F_p and energy U_p versus impact speed v_o . Δ Force; \blacktriangle Energy

penetration force increases by 7% and penetration energy by 28%. In the case of first fiber failure the force increase is 23% and the energy increase 65%, in the same speed range.

Conclusions

From the above considerations, the following conclusions may be drawn:

- Material damage due to low speed impact develops through three successive phases: (a) first fiber failure, probably preceded by delamination, (b) extended fiber breakage and (c) material penetration by the impactor.
- Macroscopic visual analysis was not capable of detecting the first failure phenomena in the reinforcement. Microscopic analysis demonstrated that material failure proceeds from the lower tensile-loaded sample surface to the higher compression-loaded surface.
- Impact curves examination allowed for the identification of the first fiber failure; the latter event is clearly evidenced by a slope decrease in the F-x curve. Reference to load drop occurrence in the F-t or F-x curves for first fiber failure identification can be misleading.
- Extended fiber breakage and material penetration were clearly identified by more or less dramatic load drops in the F-t curve.
- Material impact behaviour is influenced by test speed evidencing an increase of properties with increasing speed. In particular first fiber failure force and energy seem more rate

sensitive than penetration force and energy.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to thank CEAST Spa, Turin, Italy, that allowed for the present research to be carried out by providing the testing machine and the necessary assistance during the testing program.

Bibliography

- (1) J.C. Aleszka, "Low Energy Impact Behaviour of Composite Panels", J. Test. Eval., 6, (3), 1978, pp. 202-210
- (2) B. D. Agarwal and L. J. Broutman, Analysis and Performance of Fiber Composites, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1980
- (3) W. Goldsmith, Impact, Arnold, London, 1960
- (4) P.C. Chou, W.J. Flis and H. Miller, "Low Speed Impact of Plates of Composite Materials", Rpt. N° NADC-78259-60, Naval Air Development Center, Warminster, PA, Jan, 1978
- (5) J.P. Den Hartog, Mechanical Vibrations, Mc Graw-Hill, New York, 1947.
- (6) G. Caprino, I.Crivelli Visconti, and A.Di Ilio, "Elastic Behaviour of Composite Structures under Low Velocity Impact", Composites, Vol.15, N° 3, July 1984, pp. 231-234

